

was kept low, while it was doubled in 1991 to test the resistance in the materials. Seedlings were transplanted at 40 d. Elongation/mortality of the seedlings started 2 wk later. Data were recorded 1 1/2 mo after transplanting (see table).

Among the fine-grain varieties/lines,

Basmati 370, 4439, 1053-1-2, 1053-32, and 33608 showed resistance under low inoculum potential and high incidence under high inoculum potential. These varieties can be grown in fields with low soil infestation. Basmati 385, Basmati 6129, and 4048 are susceptible under all

conditions and should be avoided. Medium-grain varieties/lines—IR6, IR8, IR9, Shadab, KS282, PK3303-15-1, and PK1399-12-1-1-0-6—were highly resistant and can be grown successfully in severely infested fields. ■

Pathological constraints on hybrid rice production technology

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Preliminary observations during 1989 kharif (monsoon) season revealed a higher incidence of *Fusarium sheath rot* (FShR), caused by *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld., and kernel smut *Tilletia barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & Syd. on cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines than on their corresponding maintainers. We have since been observing these diseases under natural field conditions at

Percent incidence of kernel smut on CMS lines and hybrid rice and their corresponding maintainers, restorers, and inbred rice varieties.* Kapurthala, India, 1991.

Entry	Incidence (%)	Incidence on corresponding maintainer line (%)
<i>CMS line</i>		
PMS1 A	9.5	0.7
PMS2 A	10.7	0.5
PMS3 A	15.0	0.5
PMS4 A	2.9	0.6
PMS5 A	4.8	1.2
PMS6 A	0.9	0.8
PMS7 A	4.6	1.0
PMS8 A	13.9	0.5
PMS9 A	0.5	1.0
PMS10 A	7.5	0.3
<i>Hybrid rice</i>		
PAU2 A/1126-1-1	5.8	
PMS8 A/1106-6-2	10.2	
PMS8 A/31432	5.1	
PMS8 A/1126-15-3	10.0	

*Kernel smut incidence was 0.05-1.7% on restorer lines and 0.08-0.68% on inbred rice varieties (grown next to CMS lines) PR106, PR108, PR109, Jaya, Basmati 370, and Basmati 385. Incidence in Pusa Basmati No. 1 was 1.3%.

Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, and at DSST research farms.

To assess FShR severity, we randomly selected 100 tillers at five nearly equally spaced spots in a seed production plot. Disease intensity was scored on a 0-4 scale where 0 = no infection and 4 = maximum infection where no panicle emerged.

We detected kernel smut by soaking 5,000 seeds of each sample in sodium hydroxide (0.2%) solution for 20 h at 25 °C. Seeds were then washed thoroughly and spread out on blotting paper for examination.

Kernel smut and FShR were generally more severe on CMS lines and hybrid rice compared with their corresponding maintainers, restorers, and inbred rice varieties (see table). Kernel smut incidence was as high as 9.5-15.0% in CMS

lines. FShR intensity was 33.1-42.4% in CMS lines and 15.4-19.3% in maintainers, restorers, and inbred rice varieties. Panicles of CMS lines are enclosed in sheaths longer than panicles of other types of rice plants, thus providing favorable conditions for disease development. Nonexsertion of CMS panicles was 11.2-16.8% compared with 2.4-5.8% in the other groups.

The high degree of susceptibility of CMS lines to FShR and kernel smut might become a limiting factor in hybrid seed production and perhaps commercial hybrid yields. Transferring genes imparting resistance or partial resistance to kernel smut to CMS lines might be useful. We are exploring the use of chemical seed treatment and foliar sprays to check the disease. ■

High-yielding, brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant varieties developed at Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh (AP), India

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Severe BPH damage that led to hopperburn was noticed in AP in 1976. Since then, BPH has been a recurring problem in both wet (WS) and dry (DS) seasons in rice areas of East and West Godavari, Krishna, and Guntur districts. Yield losses due to BPH have ranged from 10 to 100%.

Developing BPH-resistant varieties is environment friendly and offers economic savings for farmers. Resistant donors ARC6650 and ARC5984 and popular high-yielding local variety

Sowbhagya were used in a breeding program for BPH resistance that began in the late 1970s at ARS. Selection was exercised in segregating populations of crosses Sowbhagya/ARC6650 and Sowbhagya/ARC5984, resulting in the release of six promising BPH-resistant varieties during 1986-91 (see table).

Farmers of Krishna and Godavari deltas are growing these varieties during WS on 1 million ha. They were proven superior in several yield evaluation trials at state and national levels, including the All India Coordinated Trials. ■

Characters and BPH resistance score for varieties^a bred at ARS, Maruteru, AP, India.

Variety	Parentage	Yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Test weight (g)	Seed dormancy (wk)	Grain type ^b	Reaction to BPH in field ^c	Year of release
MTU5249 (Vajram)	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	150	100	343	21.0	4	MS	3.0	1986
MTU5293 (Prathiba)	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	165	115	364	21.1	2	MS	2.0	1986
MTU2067 (Chaitanya)	Sowbhagya/ARC5984	6.5	155	110	390	21.5	4	MS	2.0	1988
MTU2077 (Krishnaveni)	Sowbhagya/ARC5984	6.5	155	110	405	19.7	4	MS	3.0	1989
MTU5182 (Nandi)	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	150	110	350	20.7	3	MS	2.0	1991
MTU4870	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	150	110	384	22.2	5	MS	2.0	-
Swarna (susceptible check)		-	150	105	360	20.0	3	MS	8.0	-

^aAll varieties have white kernels. ^bMS = medium slender. ^cScored using Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9.

Pest resistance—other pests

Susceptibility of wild rice species to nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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We tested 15 accessions of 10 wild rice species to locate sources of resistance to the rice root knot nematode, *M. graminicola*. Eight-day-old seedlings of *Oryza australiensis* from Australia; *O. barthii* and *O. brachyantha* from Africa; *O. latifolia* from South and Central America; and *O. minuta*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinalis*, *O. rhizomatis*, *O. ridleyi*, and *O. rufipogon* from Asia were infested with 1,000 2d-stage juveniles of *M. graminicola* from a culture maintained on cultivar IR72 in a greenhouse.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, with six replications, in a greenhouse using 60-cm long, 10-cm diameter PVC tubes filled with 6 kg of sterilized soil. Six plants of each accession were grown under upland conditions and watered daily. Roots were collected 48 d after infestation. Second-stage juveniles were extracted by placing the roots in a misting chamber for 7 d. Results were analyzed

using ANOVA and DMRT.

M. graminicola reproduced on all of the wild rice species tested, indicating that none were resistant to the parasite (see table). Different degrees of susceptibility, however, were observed.

Average number of *M. graminicola* 2d-stage juveniles recovered from 1 g of root.

Wild rice species tested (accession no.)	<i>M. graminicola</i> juveniles recovered from 1 g of root ^a (av no.)
<i>O. australiensis</i> (100882)	10236 c
<i>O. barthii</i> (101827)	1672 a
<i>O. brachyantha</i> (101232)	5855 b
<i>O. latifolia</i> (100914)	761 a
<i>O. latifolia</i> (105141)	505 a
<i>O. latifolia</i> (105142)	469 a
<i>O. minuta</i> (101141)	1362 a
<i>O. nivara</i> (103422)	1024 a
<i>O. nivara</i> (103839)	3209 ab
<i>O. officinalis</i> (100896)	238 a
<i>O. rhizomatis</i> (105432)	650 a
<i>O. ridleyi</i> (100821)	452 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (100692)	872 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (103817)	965 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (104453)	396 a

^aAv of six replications. Averages followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

O. australiensis and *O. brachyantha* allowed greater reproduction of the parasite than did the other accessions. We will need to test other wild rice species and accessions of species previously tested to determine whether absolute resistance to rice root knot nematode exists in the genus *Oryza*. ■

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